

Synthesis of Thioureas from 6-Amino- and 8-Amino-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins

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Substituted thioureas have been reported to possess a wide variety of pharmacological activities, viz., antituberculous, antithyroid, hypnotic, anaesthetic, anthelmintic, antibacterial, insecticidal, rodenticidal, antidiabetic, and antispasmodic.¹ Buu-Hoi *et al.*² and Weinstein *et al.*³ have observed antiviral activity in some of the compounds of this class. Thiourea derivatives are also found effective in the prevention of radiation sickness⁴. Coumarins are well known for their biochemical properties⁵. It was therefore considered worthwhile to prepare thioureas from coumarins.

In the present communication is reported the synthesis of thioureas from 6-amino- and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins. Thioureas were prepared by refluxing a solution of equimolecular amounts of the aminocoumarin and aryl isothiocyanate⁶ and crystallised from ethanol (Table I).

TABLE I

Thioureas from 6- and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins.

No.	R.	Formula.	From 6-Amino derivative.			From 8-Amino derivative.		
			M.P.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.
1	Ph	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	190°	9.75	9.81	> 300°	9.83	9.81
2	<i>o</i> -Tol	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	185°	9.39	9.41	257°	9.46	9.41
3	<i>m</i> -Tol	"	270°	9.45	"	268°	9.53	"
4	<i>p</i> -Tol	"	268°	9.37	"	182°	9.36	"
5	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>o</i>)	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	197°	8.90	8.87	192°	8.89	8.87
6	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i>)	"	170°	8.91	"	> 300°	8.84	"
7	C ₆ H ₄ OMe (<i>o</i>)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	230°	8.95	8.98	246°	8.94	8.98
8	C ₆ H ₄ OMe (<i>p</i>)	"	175°	8.93	"	280°	8.92	"

N. B. All melting points are uncorrected.

1. Schroeder, *Chem. Rev.*, 1955, 55, 183.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2160; 1958, 2815.
3. "Antibiotics and Chemotherapy", 1957, 7, 443.
4. Semenov and Prokudina, *Med. Radiol.*, 1958, 1, 70.
5. Bone, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 367.
6. Bu-Hoi *et al. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1573.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin on nitration by the procedure of Shah and Mehta⁷ furnished 6-nitro- and 8-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins, which on reduction with sodium hydrosulphite provided the corresponding aminocoumarins.

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7. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 784.